

Academic Review of Bipolar Disorder's Relationship with Depression, as well as Triggers and Solutions

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To cite this article, Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 3-5, 2023, p. 126 – 152. - 0099-0001-2303-0501.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

It is believed that around four percent of the population in industrialized nations throughout the globe suffers from bipolar disorder (BD). Unfortunatously, a sizeable number of patients either do not obtain a diagnosis at all, receive a diagnosis that is incorrect, or receive therapy that is insufficient for their disease. Adolescence or the early adult years are often the times in a person's life when they first become aware of any symptoms. The disorder is characterized by periods of "mood" that are either manic (periods of hyperactivity associated with high energy and risky behavior) or depressive in nature, with periods of relative normalcy in between. Manic depression is characterized by periods of hyperactivity associated with high energy and risky behavior. The mental illness known as manic depression is characterized by episodes of hyperactivity that are accompanied by high levels of energy and dangerous activities. A person who is experiencing a manic episode may feel much more assured, restless, or irritated than they often do. It's possible

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that the individual may participate in impulsive activities that put them in potentially dangerous situations, such as abandoning their job, throwing away their money, or initiating a fight with someone else. Because of the decreased need for sleep that occurs during manic episodes, it is far more probable that manic episodes may reoccur in the future. It's possible that the manic phase of bipolar disorder (BD) is less detrimental, if not more so, than the depression phase of the condition. The majority of persons who have bipolar illness will suffer from more periods of depression than manic ones, and depressive episodes will often last for a longer period of time. In addition, the majority of persons who have this illness seek treatment for their depression when they are in the middle of an episode of depression; this is one factor that leads to the common occurrence of incorrect diagnoses of major depressive disorder. According to the intensity of the presenting symptoms, bipolar illness may be divided into two distinct subtypes: bipolar 1 and bipolar 2. It is possible for a person who has been diagnosed with bipolar 1 to have a depressive episode; however, experiencing a depressive episode is not necessary for a diagnosis of bipolar disorder. On the other side, a person who has bipolar 2 will at some point in their life undergo a significant depressive episode.

Keywords: *Bipolar Disorder, Depression, BD, BD Diagnosis, BD Treatment*

Introduction

Since BD has such a significant impact on a person's state of mind, it is often co-occurring with other mental health issues, such as anxiety and drug misuse, which may make treatment challenging. Self-medicating with alcohol is associated with a significant increase in the risk of worsening depressive episodes and chronic physical health conditions (such as obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, hepatitis, and obstructive sleep apnea), all of which are more likely to be found in people who suffer from bipolar disorder (BD).

The impacts of BD may have a negative impact, not only on personal relationships, but also on obligations. Manic episodes, which may be experienced by someone suffering from bipolar illness, can cause that individual to become more argumentative, irritable, and nasty.

Normal disagreements have the potential to become arguments that cannot be resolved logically and may even escalate, as the findings of a study titled "Impact of Bipolar Affective Disorders On

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Family and Partners" that was published in The Journal of Affective Disorders in 2001 found. The study was titled "Impact of Bipolar Affective Disorders On Family and Partners." As a consequence of this, caregivers and friends of individuals who have manic episodes may get the false feeling that they are in danger since people who experience manic episodes often act in ways that are unexpected. When a person has this diagnosis, it is much more difficult for them to keep their impulses under control and to operate regularly in life and social interactions. This is particularly true in the case when they lack the information and abilities necessary to manage in a healthy manner. These kinds of issues may be so debilitating that they increase the likelihood of unemployment as well as the rate of marriage dissolution.

Method

According to the findings of a study that was conducted in 2014 and published in Psychiatry Online under the title "Participation Patterns of Justice Among People with Schizophrenia and Bipolar Disorder: Significant Risk Factors," a diagnosis of bipolar disorder may also be associated with increased rates of incarceration. While attempting to bring their symptoms under control, those who suffer from bipolar illness may have the sense of being powerless and alone. Those who have bipolar illness may still lead a normal life if they have the support of a community and are able to learn how to manage their symptoms in order to avoid further relapses of the disease.

Treatment

A person who suffers from bipolar disorder could feel particularly well at one moment, but after some time they might withdraw and isolate themselves. Mood fluctuations that are compatible with a clinical diagnosis of manic depression may be experienced by a person who has been diagnosed with bipolar disease. As a result, the evaluation performed by psychologists is considered to be of utmost significance throughout the phase of the illness diagnosis. The most distinguishing characteristic of bipolar illness is an individual's tendency to experience significant shifts in mood, going from one pole to the other. A person with bipolar illness who is going through a manic phase will be exceedingly hyperactive and will say they are feeling incredibly happy with their lives. On the other hand, if he were to slip into a state of depression, he might isolate himself from the rest of the world, and he might even experience urges to hurt himself or take his own life.

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Bipolar Patients Not Receiving Modern Treatment

Bipolar individuals not getting current therapy may endure recurring manic or depressed episodes. People with severe bipolar disease may have difficulty detecting the symptoms of their condition on their own, despite the fact that most individuals are able to identify the signs and symptoms of mood disorders. The genes of an individual may be responsible for the development of bipolar disorder, but a person might also develop the condition later in life as a response to stressful events. The disease known as bipolar disorder is present in a significant number of the people who go to their physicians complaining of depression. Causes Nevertheless, it is considered that a combination of a number of risk factors must be present in order for a person to be diagnosed with bipolar disorder. While the specific etiology of bipolar illness is unknown, it is believed that a combination of risk factors is required. Chemical abnormalities in the brain, hereditary transmission, and trigger factors are some examples of these aspects; nevertheless, this list is not exhaustive.

The Brain's Unbalanced Chemical Composition

There is evidence that suggests that chemical imbalances in the brain may have a role in the development of bipolar illness. Neurotransmitters are the names given to the substances that are accountable for governing the functioning of the brain. Neurotransmitters play a critical role in the regulation of brain activity. If there is an imbalance in one or more of the neurotransmitters, then it is possible for a person to develop signs of bipolar disorder. Symptoms of bipolar disorder include extreme shifts in mood and energy levels. If there is a genetic connection between people who are afflicted by bipolar illness, then the condition may run in families. It's possible that beneficial results may be attributed, in certain cases, to the transfer of genes within a family between first-degree relatives. Those who have a parent, child, or sibling who has been diagnosed with bipolar disease need to get medical assistance as quickly as they can.

Bipolar Disorder Cannot Cause a Single Gene

The origin of bipolar illness cannot be traced back to a single gene, which is a very unfortunate fact. Instead, it is believed that specific genetic characteristics and environmental factors have a role in functioning as triggers for the disease.

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Triggers

There is a substantial link between traumatic experiences or stressful situations and the mental condition known as bipolar disorder. The termination of a meaningful relationship, physical, sexual, or emotional abuse, the death of a close family member or loved one, or a brain injury are all examples of life events that have the potential to set off bipolar disorder in a person. These kinds of transformative events in a person's life have the ability to bring on episodes of melancholy at any time in that person's life.

Symptoms

The condition that is referred to as bipolar disorder is a severe sickness. It is possible for a person who is struggling with bipolar disease to be unaware that they have entered the manic phase of the ailment at this time. After the end of the manic period, the individual will enter the following phase, which consists of reevaluating their actions. Many individuals who are affected by bipolar illness are aware that they have the condition as a result of the warnings given to them by others in their immediate environment.

Individuals who have been diagnosed with an advanced stage of bipolar disease may have episodes that are both more intense and more frequent than those experienced by other people. Because of this, a person's job life, friendships, family life, and intimate ties might all be negatively impacted. Individuals who suffer from bipolar disorder have an increased risk of experiencing hallucinations and other strange experiences, such as seeing, hearing, or smelling things that are not there, particularly during the manic and depressive periods of the condition. They may also have ideas (delusions) that are unintelligible to others and impossible for them to comprehend.

Is the phrase that practitioners of medicine use to refer to these kinds of symptoms. The symptoms of bipolar illness may cause unexpected changes in a person's mood or conduct, both of which can lead to substantial problems in a person's day-to-day life. Bipolar disorder symptoms can also lead to considerable issues in relationships. During the manic phase of the condition, those who have bipolar disorder may experience great enthusiasm and enjoyment.

1. *The feeling of being at the epicenter of everything that happens*
2. *Hyperactivity*

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3. *Less sleep than before*
4. *Less shyness in sexual behavior*
5. *Increased overconfidence*
6. *Difficulty maintaining concentration*
7. *Hallucinations*
8. *Jabber*
9. *Creativity*
10. *Alcohol and drug use*
11. *Impatience*
12. *Constantly dispose of hard-earned money*
13. *Severe feelings of restlessness*
14. *In the depressive phase, a strong desire to sleep for a long time*
15. *Tiredness*
16. *Unhappiness*
17. *Difficulty focusing attention on what's going on*
18. *Occasional pangs of regret*
19. *Hopelessness and a constant state of uncertainty*
20. *Anorexia*
21. *delusions*
22. *Difficulty falling asleep or staying asleep*
23. *Frequent disagreements*
24. *Decreased desire for sexual activity*
25. *Thoughts of ending one's own life*
26. *Inability to perform activities of daily living*

Literature Studies

The symptoms of both episodes are often noticeable to the patient. The length of time that this stage lasts might range anywhere from a few hours to many days. Even if the individual is in a very upbeat frame of mind at the moment, there is a strong chance that they will start to question their abilities once a certain amount of time has passed.

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Diagnostic Techniques

In many cases, a diagnosis of bipolar disorder may be made based only on the patient's clinical presentation when combined with the patient's family medical history. The nature of an individual's first manic or depressive episode is one of the criteria used to establish a diagnosis of bipolar disorder in a person.

If a person's first manifestation of a mental disease is depression, it may be difficult to determine whether or not they have bipolar disorder as their underlying condition. Seeing both manic and depressed episodes in a patient suffering from bipolar disorder is required in order to arrive at a conclusive diagnosis of the condition. A diagnosis of bipolar illness may bring on a condition of confusion in certain people, particularly under certain circumstances. If the patient in question has issues such as alcohol or drug misuse, getting an accurate diagnosis may be more challenging. Keeping track of the patient's attack times is the most vital component of this scenario. This is due to the fact that bipolar illness might be mistaken with other conditions that are part of their own group.

- "Has the patient ever considered harming himself when he is manic or hypomanic?" And
- "Is there anyone else in the patient's family who has been diagnosed with bipolar disorder?" Ask the psychiatrist.

The attending physician may suggest a variety of various tests for the patient, taking into consideration the patient's condition of having a thyroid that is hyperactive. Likewise, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and other imaging modalities may be used in order to investigate the processes that are carried out in the brain.

Various Ways of Treatment

The engagement of the patient in the treatment process, as well as the support of the patient's family members and the attending physician, are all highly crucial aspects of the management of bipolar illness. The patient may not be aware of what they are feeling, what they are experiencing, or what changes are taking place in them when the attacks are really severe. It is possible for a patient who is suffering from bipolar disease to not detect any changes in their health until the illness has progressed to a more severe state.

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During the manic phase, the patient may have a tendency to continuously complain of being unhappy and not being able to enjoy life, despite the fact that he or she may not understand why they feel this way. Mania, on the other hand, is a phase that is often noticed by people who are around the person who is experiencing it. At this juncture, assault times are of the utmost significance. Antidepressants and medications that stabilize mood are often administered to a patient who is experiencing an episode of major depression if it is judged that the patient is in a depressed state. During the manic phase of the disease, antipsychotic medication may be provided to the patient if there is a history of psychotic symptoms. Between episodes of manic or hypomanic depressive states, a person who suffers from the mental disease known as bipolar disorder may have a fairly normal existence.

Not only does the treatment approach help to halt assaults after they have already taken place, but it also works to prevent attacks from taking place. In this regard, mood stabilizers are of critical significance. Individuals who have been diagnosed with bipolar illness sometimes, after a period of time, come to the conclusion that they no longer need the treatment with medication because they are feeling better. In this particular scenario, the manner in which the patient's family communicates with the patient is of the utmost significance.

It is of the utmost importance for the patient's family members to have a deep degree of comprehension of the discourses that support the use of medications, particularly in terms of the assaults of the illness.

Mania

Excessive elation (mania), on the other hand, is a sign of one of these phases of the illness, whilst sadness is a symptom of the other (depression). The course of these two disease stages, which seem to be mirror reflections of each other, is marked by remissions and exacerbations at various points along the way. The patient instantly returns to normal, with the exception of times when the patient is experiencing discomfort. Some individuals continue to experience their initial symptoms, which may have a marginal impact on their day-to-day lives. Patients are making improvement, despite the fact that some of them continue to live. During the manic or exuberant phase of the disease, the patient's mood is greatly elevated, and he becomes too pleased about everything. This phase of the condition may also be referred to as the phase of the condition. This stage is designed

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to assist patients in coping with the various phases of their sickness. At this period, the patient displayed symptoms such as exaggerating the significance of ungrounded ideas or projects, feeling much higher than they actually are, experiencing notions of grandeur, and fast flow of thoughts in the patient's head, including the following:

1. *Feeling overly energetic*
2. *Decreased need for sleep or even denial of need for sleep and*
3. *Engaging in exciting or fun activities without thinking about the consequences*

Examples of symptoms include spending too much money and driving at unsafe high speeds.

On the other side, the circumstance that was stated above is the antithesis of what takes place during times of despair or depression. Symptoms that may be associated with depression include unhappiness, pessimism, hopelessness, low self-esteem, feelings of worthlessness, exaggerated feelings of guilt or regret, changes in pleasure from activities that were once enjoyed, changes such as loss of appetite or insomnia, thoughts of death and suicide, and unexplained pain in the body. ("Bipolar Disorder 0539 70 70 182 - akademitms.com") The prevalence of bipolar disorder is around 2% to 3% overall and is not affected by a culture's level of development. There is not a discernible difference in the number of women who are affected at a young age, and the typical age of onset falls somewhere in the range of 20 to 25 years old.

Findings

It has been shown that hereditary factors have a significant part in the progression of the illness, and it has also been demonstrated that genetic factors are, on average, effective. It is the underlying cause of around 66 percent of all occurrences of the illness. Alterations in the transit or levels of chemical molecules that allow intercellular communication in the brain are yet another cause for this phenomenon. The transmission in the brain is disrupted as a result of these alterations, which in turn has an influence on the regulation of cognition, memory, learning, and mood. In addition, traumatic or stressful situations may be a role in the start of the first illness phase of bipolar disorder, and they can also worsen the causes of the disease. Both of these effects can be a result of the disorder's dual nature. Experiences such as funerals, job losses, the birth of additional children, and members of the family moving away may all be life-changing moments for a family.

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One of the most crucial characteristics that will influence the course of bipolar disorder is whether or not it is seasonal. Patients have a propensity to experience joy and enthusiasm throughout the spring and summer months; nevertheless, during the autumn and winter months, they tend to feel depressed and trapped in life. This occurs only during the winter months. It has been observed that the season that is most likely to result in a deterioration of the patients' health is the one that occurs between spring and summer, namely the transition from one to the other.

As a result of this cyclical phenomena, about one-fourth of patients report a deterioration of their condition between the last days of spring and the first days of summer. It is essential, at these times when things are going poorly, to avoid underestimating impulsive and reactionary movements, a surge in hostility, outbursts of rage, excessive spending, and excitement.

In addition to this, there is a noticeable rise in the frequency of conduct that may be classified as hostile. In addition to this, a person may, on occasion, engage in actions that are characterized as having suicidal inclinations or, more precisely, as engaging in activities that cause damage to themselves. Although if the suicide rate isn't very high during this time period, it is nevertheless in everyone's best interest to exercise extreme caution due of the elevated risk. As a consequence of this, patients have a relatively low threshold for being ill at this time of year, and as a consequence of this, they face the risk of showing behaviors that put both themselves and their surroundings in danger. In order to effectively treat patients who suffer from bipolar disorder, it is necessary to make use of a number of different pharmacological medicines. Throughout the first ten years after contracting the condition, the majority of people would suffer from four different ailments on average.

After the first decade has passed, the average amount of time that passes between illness episodes is between one and two years. In the absence of therapy for the underlying condition, manic episodes often continue for a period of at least a few months on average. Untreated depression often persists for a minimum of six months before a person seeks therapy for it. Between attacks of their illness, many patients are able to return to feeling quite normal. Some people see life with pessimism or have no real interest in it at all. On the other hand, the longest period between disease attacks tends to be the most typical symptom in the early years of the disease; however, as the

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disease progresses, this period tends to shorten significantly. This is the case because it is the longest period between disease attacks in the early years of the disease. Since there is no one therapy that is effective for all patients with bipolar disorder, tailored treatment regimens are designed for each patient in conjunction with the patient's primary care physician. This treatment method involves putting one's life in order, avoiding malnutrition and habits of alcohol and drug abuse, establishing positive thinking and behavioral skills, learning ways for dealing with stress, and having full knowledge on the progression of the illness.

The mood and energy levels of someone with BP might fluctuate wildly from one moment to the next (Merikangas et al. 2011). Because hypertension is a chronic and recurrent disease, it is linked to decreased functional ability, cognitive impairment, and quality of life (QoL) (Martnez-Arán et al. 2004; Michalak et al. 2005; Bonnin et al., 2012). This is due to the fact that hypertension is a persistent and recurrent disease. Not only are academics and clinicians concentrating their efforts on clinical rehabilitation as a result of the intricacy and ramifications of this condition, but they are also concentrating their efforts on functional recovery and, more recently, well-being (Vieta and Torrent, 2016). This new way of thinking takes into consideration not only the alleviation of symptoms, but also the return to normal functioning and the pursuit of a meaningful life as well. In point of fact, Dion and colleagues had already pointed out in 1988 that factors other than symptoms are associated with the functioning of patients with BP, and that treatment must be aimed at relieving symptoms in addition to reducing patient disability in order to be effective in treatment (Dion et al., 1988).

Even after the patient has had their first manic episode, it is known that only one patient out of every three would restore their psychosocial functioning in a one-year follow-up (Tohen et al. 2000). It is vital to present a quick description of both of these problems as a consequence of the numerous initiatives that have been conducted over the last decade to enhance functioning and well-being in BP. These efforts may be found throughout the previous decade.

Argument

There is not a universal agreement on how to define psychosocial functioning, despite the fact that it is of the utmost significance in BD. According to the findings of a research that was conducted

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in 2009 by Tohen and colleagues on behalf of the International Bipolar Association Task Group, there were several potential definitions of psychosocial functioning evaluated, but none of them were unanimously agreed upon. As an example, specialists used the definition that is provided by the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF). According to this interpretation, functionality may be broken down into three distinct categories, which are as follows:

1. *Body structures and functions;*
2. *Events and participation and*
3. *Personal environmental factors*

In addition, the authors of these guidelines emphasized that this construct is difficult to measure and that, in addition to the ICF, the Short Test of Functioning Assessment (FAST) scale (Rosa et al., 2007) may constitute a good approach to measuring functionality. This statement was made in light of the fact that Rosa et al., 2007 published a study suggesting that the FAST scale is a good approach to measuring functionality. The FAST scale was first published by Rosa et al. in 2007. (Tohen et al. 2009). Before these guidelines were made, there were a great deal of efforts put forward to define psychosocial functioning. For instance, Zarate and colleagues suggested in the year 2000 that the evaluation of psychosocial functioning should cover a variety of different behavioral domains. A person's ability to operate socially or professionally, to live independently, and to have a love life are all examples of talents that fall under this category. The traditional definition of functional recovery is the return to regular role functioning in the areas that are the subject of the research (Zarate et al., 2000).

Since at that time psychosocial functioning was evaluated using the Global Assessment Functioning Scale (GAF), which was supported by the various versions of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, this approach was a major breakthrough in the profession (DSM). The GAF simply provides a single score and does not discriminate between Zarate and the numerous distinct behavioral domains that its colleagues have found. In spite of this, it is at least the clinical rating scale that is employed the most often to monitor progression of illness (Von Korff et al. 2011).

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Graph: 1 - Graph showing the differences between bipolar I disorder, bipolar II disorder and cyclothymia.¹

The FAST scale, which was discussed before, was established in 2007 by Rosa and her colleagues as a tool for monitoring functioning. It is intended to evaluate the most typical difficulties experienced by those who have been diagnosed with bipolar illness. This scale was designed with the intention of conforming to the concept of functionality that was published in 2000 by Zarate and colleagues. This concept places a significant emphasis on the evaluation of a variety of behavioral domains. To be more specific, FAST takes into consideration the following domains: autonomy, vocational functioning, cognitive functioning, financial concerns, interpersonal functioning, and leisure. In this perspective, FAST has various advantages over GAF, such as investigating additional behavioral domains, not rating symptomatology, and being unique to BP. Moreover, FAST was developed more recently than GAF. The DSM-5 does not currently endorse the use of the GAF under any circumstances.

¹ Evidence-based assessment/Rx4DxTx of bipolar in youths – Wikiversity

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GAF and FAST, on the other hand, are exclusively concerned with the impact that mental disorders have on functioning. These are therapeutic techniques that do not take into consideration the limits that are caused by physical circumstances or the environment around them (Vieta et al. 2007; Ayuso-Mateos et al. 2013). These clinical instruments may be self-administered (WHODAS 2.0), or they can be delivered by the evaluator (GAF, FAST, ICF core sets). In addition to these methods, there are other other approaches (Patterson et al., 2001). Performance on a given task serves as a measurement of one's functional capability here. This test measures your ability to comprehend and do activities that are common in communities, such as budgeting, communicating, moving about, maintaining your house, and managing your mobility.

Chart: 2 - Understanding Bipolar Disorder - Emotional Consultation.²

The evaluation of psychosocial functioning as a whole in people with BD only gives it a marginal amount of weight. Despite this, it is a faithful representation of the incredible diversity that can be found out there. It is possible for the investigator or the clinician to explain psychosocial

² <https://affective-counseling.com/2022/11/understanding-bipolar-disorder/>

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functioning in a manner that has an effect on the instrument that is used to test it; nevertheless, the opposite is also true:

It is possible to get insight into how the concept of psychosocial functioning is perceived based on which instrument is favored more than the other. It would be preferable to assess psychosocial functioning from three separate viewpoints at the same time in order to circumvent this difficulty.

These views are as follows:

- (1) *a subjective perspective using a self-administered scale such as the Sheehan Disability Scale for BP (SDS), Arbuckle et al., 2009);*
- (2) *A semi-objective scale using FAST, GAF, or LIFE-RIFT (Leon et al., 1999), where the interviewer grades patients based on their response, and finally*
- (3) *An objective measure of performance-based and functional capacity, such as UPSA.*

By using these three alternate methods, it will be possible to uncover all of the components associated with the functional impairment identified in BP.

Factors That May Affect the Patient's Functional Outcome in BP

It has been shown that a broad range of variables, including demographic, clinical, and neuropsychological factors, are linked with functional outcome in BD. [Citation needed] (Berns et al., 2007). (Tohen et al., 1990; Sanchez-Moreno et al., 2018) and elderly patients (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 2018) demonstrate inferior functional results than women (Tohen et al., 1990; Sanchez-Moreno et al., 2018).

On the other hand, being married can provide a protective barrier against the beginning of functional impairment (Kupfer et al. 2002; Wingo et al. 2010). A greater socioeconomic position, as assessed by criteria such as education and employment, was connected not just with better functional results, but also with these outcomes (Keck et al., 1998; Wingo et al., 2010). In terms of clinical variables, the presence of subsyndrome depressive symptoms has been reported as the single most important factor associated with functional impairment (Tohen et al. 1990; Bonn et al. 2010, 2012; Gitlin et al. 2011; Gutiérrez-Rojas et al. 2011). This has been the case across multiple

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studies (Tohen et al. 1990; Bonn et al. 2010, 2012; Bonn et al. ; Reinares et al ., 2013; Samalin et al., 2016; Murru et al.; Huxley and Baldessarini, 2007; Sanchez-Moreno et al., 2009a, 2010; Reinares et al., 2013; Etain et al., 2017; Murru et al. others, 2018).

In particular, people who have psychiatric comorbidity, substance use disorder (such as an addiction to alcohol or cannabis), and personality disorders may also have a negative impact on the functional outcomes of BD patients (Sánchez-Moreno et al. 2009b; Leen et al., 2013; Icick et al. 2017); Kizilkurt et al. 2018; Williams & Simms, 2018).

Several studies have reported that it is a good indicator of functional outcome; however, variables related to other neurocognitive domains, such as executive functions, processing speed, and attention (Martinez-Aran et al. 2007; Bonnn et al., 2010, 2014, Torres et al. 2011; Jiménez- López et al., 2018) have been shown to be more important in determining functional outcome. In terms of the neurocognitive variables that remain, the last one is verbal memory (Jaeger et al. 2007; Mur et al. 2009; Wingo et al. 2010).

Bipolar Disorder

It is conceivable to state that the neurocognitive elements impacting the functional result in bipolar disorder may change according to the developmental stage of the illness. This is something that is feasible to say since it is possible to say that the functional outcome in bipolar disorder may vary. Those who are diagnosed with the condition while it is still in its early stages, for instance, tend to have a less generalized kind of cognitive impairment. This indicates that one year following the commencement of the first manic episode, some cognitive domains, such as processing speed and executive skills, may emerge in these people (Torres et al., 2014). In this context, at least two studies have demonstrated that patients who have had their initial episode of schizophrenia and have not had any relapses may see an improvement in their neurocognitive skills over a follow-up period of one year (Kozicky et al. 2014; Demmo et al. 2018). In conclusion, preserving neurocognition from the very start of the illness might potentially ensure better functional results.

Restoring Psychosocial Functioning

The research on therapies, both pharmaceutical and nonpharmacological, to restore functioning in BD is still in its early stages. As was mentioned earlier, there is a well-established connection

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between functional outcomes and neurocognition. As a result of this connection, numerous efforts have been made in recent years to enhance cognitive development. These efforts include the use of pharmaceutical and psychological treatments. In point of fact, due to recent developments in pharmacological therapies, the focus of these interventions has switched from the restoration of psychosocial functioning to the restoration of cognitive function. Erythropoietin, mifepristone, and lurasidone are three of the most promising medicinal therapies that have been found to enhance cognitive performance in people who have been diagnosed with bipolar illness (Watson et al., 2012; Yatham et al., 2017). (Miskowiak et al., 2014, 2015).

Because of the connection that exists between neurocognition and psychosocial functioning, it is probable that any efforts made to enhance neurocognition will also result in an improvement in functional outcome. On the other hand, there have been no research efforts focused on pharmaceutical therapies that address both of these issues at the same time. It is essential to keep in mind that the methodological guidelines for cognitive studies that have been offered advise incorporating a functional measure as a vital secondary outcome (Miskowiak et al., 2017). In this context, a functional improvement that enables the tool to assess and classify patients into distinct groups based on their functional performance may be valuable in determining whether or not these therapies are successful (Bonn et al. 2018a).

Psychological Treatments and Methods

In addition to the use of pharmaceutical medications, there have been a number of recent initiatives undertaken in the area of psychological interventions to develop treatments with the purpose of restoring psychosocial functioning in persons who have bipolar illness. The first step of the project was to conduct a test on the general public using a piece of software called Cognitive Rehabilitation (Deckersbach et al., 2010). Even more intriguing is the fact that the results demonstrate that improvements in executive function may be partly ascribed to rises in professional competence. The first randomized controlled trial (RCT) of a therapy that was extremely similar to the one that was being examined was carried out by Torrent and colleagues in 2013. (Torrent et al., 2013).

It has been shown that functional remediation, commonly known as FR, is helpful in improving functional outcomes in euthymic patients who began therapy with moderate to severe functional impairment. In addition to this, it was shown that the improvement in psychosocial functioning

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was maintained during the 6-month follow-up period (Bonnin et al. 2016). The intervention did not seem to have much of an effect on the individual's level of cognitive, which is unfortunate.

Functional restoration (FR) is a therapy modality that focuses primarily on functional improvement, in contrast to other therapies that are classified as "cognitive improvement" treatments. It places a significant emphasis on the training of neurocognitive skills that are helpful in performing day-to-day tasks.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, it is possible that this approach is suitable for some individuals, particularly those who are in the latter stages of the illness and those who have moderate to severe functional impairment (Zyto et al. 2016). On the other hand, research has shown that not all treatments for cognitive rehabilitation can lead to an improvement in functional result. For instance, a randomized controlled experiment (RCT) that was carried out by Demant et al (2015) indicated that after 12 weeks of intervention, there was no improvement in either the cognitive or functional result. It is essential to point out that these disappointing outcomes might be rationalized by a number of methodological constraints imposed on the experiment. One of these limitations may be the length of time the intervention was carried out for (if it was too brief), or the fact that patients could have been subsyndromic when they were enrolled. An additional research was carried out by Lewandowski et al. (2017), and it examined the efficacy of an internet-based cognitive improvement program in patients with BD who were part of an active control group. This study looked at neurocognition as well as community functioning. Patients who participated in an internet-based program demonstrated increases in their cognitive function after receiving treatment. These benefits were shown across a variety of cognitive domains, including processing speed, visual learning and memory, and the composite score. At the conclusion of the session, a period of time spanning six months was used to monitor whether or not these outcomes had changed. Nevertheless, there was no correlation between the intervention and any changes in the functioning of the community. On the other hand, cognitive change was correlated with functional change throughout the sample. Additional research centered on the brain's cognitive processes is now being conducted, and some of these studies involve programs for action-based cognitive rehabilitation. The education on computers in these programs is supplemented by a variety of

hands-on activities and tough mental challenges that take place both during and between class sessions. This cutting-edge method is anticipated to be more successful in enhancing functional results than more conventional forms of cognitive rehabilitation (Bowie et al., 2017; Ott et al., 2018). It is difficult to quantify the efficiency of these current strategies in improving functioning since very few studies utilize psychosocial functioning as the major result of their study. In this context, there is an urgent need for meta-analyses that are capable of providing this data.

References

- American Psychiatric Association. Bipolar and Related Disorders. In: Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders : DSM-5. Arlington, VA, 2013. [Google Scholar]
- Merikangas KR, Jin R, He JP, et al. Prevalence and correlates of bipolar spectrum disorder in the world mental health survey initiative. *Arch Gene Psychiatry* 2011;68:241–51. 10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2011.12 [PMC free article]
- McElroy S.L. Diagnosing and treating comorbid (complicated) bipolar disorder. *J Clin Psychiatry* 2004;65(Suppl 15):35–44. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Perron BE, Bohnert ASB, Vaughn MG, et al. Profiles of disability among adults with bipolar spectrum disorders. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol* 2010;45:1125–34. 10.1007/s00127-009-0153-y
- Comes M, Rosa A, Reinares M, et al. Functional impairment in older adults with bipolar disorder. *J Nerv Ment Dis* 2017;205:443–7. 10.1097/NMD.0000000000000683
- Liberati A, Altman DG, Tetzlaff J, et al. The PRISMA statement for reporting systematic reviews and meta-analysis of studies that evaluate health care interventions: explanation and elaboration. *PLoS Med* 2009;6:e1000100. 10.1371/journal.pmed.1000100 [PMC free article]
- McGowan J, Sampson M, Salzwedel DM, et al. PRESS Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Statement. *J Clin Epidemiol*

2016;75:40–6.

10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.01.021

Tufanaru C, Munn Z, Aromataris E. Chapter 3: Systematic reviews of effectiveness. In: Aromataris E, Munn Z, eds. Joanna Briggs Institute Reviewer's Manual. ("Nursing strategies for pressure injury prevention in surgical patients") The Joanna Briggs Institute, 2017. <https://reviewersmanual.joannabriggs.org/> [Google Scholar]

Deeks JJ, Higgins JPT, Altman DG. Chapter 10: Analyzing data and undertaking meta-analyses. In: Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, et al., eds. Cochrane Handbook for systematic reviews of interventions version 6.2 (updated February 2021). Cochrane, 2021. www.training.cochrane.org/handbook [Google Scholar]

Kebede D, Alem A, Shibire T, Deyassa N, Negash A, Beyero T, Medhin G, Fekadu A. Symptomatic and functional outcome of bipolar disorder in Butajira Ethiopia. *J Affect Disord.* 2006;90(2–3):239–49.

Saarni SI, Viertio S, Perälä J, Koskinen S, Lönnqvist J, Suvisaari J. Quality of life of people with schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and other psychotic disorders. *BrJ Psychiatry.* 2010;197(5):386–94.

Gutiérrez-Rojas L, Gurpegui M, Ayuso-Mateos JL, Gutiérrez-Ariza JA, Ruiz-Veguilla M, Jurado D. Quality of life in bipolar disorder patients: a comparison with a general population sample. *Bipolar Discord.* 2008;10(5):625–34.

Studart P, Galvão-de Almeida A, Bezerra-Filho S, Caribé A, Afonso NR, Daltro C, Miranda-Scippa Â. Is history of suicidal behavior related to social support and quality of life in outpatients with bipolar I disorder? *Psychiatry Res.* 2016;246:796–802.

"Berlim MT, Pargendler J, Caldieraro MA, Almeida EA, Fleck MP, Joiner TE." ("Health-related quality of life among patients with bipolar disorder in ...") Quality of life in unipolar and bipolar depression: Are there significant differences? *J Nerv Ment Dis.* 2004;192(11):792–5.

- Berlim MT, Mattevi BS, Pavanello DP, Caldieraro MA, Fleck MP. Suicidal ideation and quality of life among adult Brazilian outpatients with depressive disorders. *J Nerv Ment Dis.* 2003;191(3):193–7.
- Koivumaa-Honkanen H, Honkanen R, Viinamaeki H, Heikkilae K, Kaprio J, Koskenvuo M. Life satisfaction and suicide: a 20-year follow-up study. *AmJ Psychiatry.* 2001;158(3):433–9.
- Judd LL, Akiskal HS, Schettler PJ, Endicott J, Maser J, Solomon DA, Leon AC, Rice JA, Keller MB. The long-term natural history of the weekly symptomatic status of bipolar I disorder. *Arch Gene Psychiatry.* 2002;59(6):530–7.
- Tohen M, Wateraux CM, Tsuang MT. Outcome in mania: a 4-year prospective follow-up of seventy-five patients utilizing survival analysis. *Arch Gene Psychiatry.* 1990;47(12):1106–11.
- Nehme E, Obeid S, Hallit S, Haddad C, Salame W, Tahan F. Impact of psychosis in bipolar disorder during manic episodes. *IntJ Neurosci.* 2018;128(12):1128–34.
- Bora E, Vahip S, Akdeniz F, Gonul AS, Eryavuz A, Ogut M, Alkan M. The effect of previous psychotic mood episodes on cognitive impairment in euthymic bipolar patients. *Bipolar Discord.* 2007;9(5):468–7
- Conus P, Cotton S, Abdel-Baki A, Lambert M, Berk M, McGorry PD. Symptomatic and functional outcome 12 months after a first episode of psychotic mania: barriers to recovery in a catchment area sample. *Bipolar Discord.* 2006;8(3):221–31.
- de la Cruz MSD, Lai Z, Goodrich DE, Kilbourne AM. Gender differences in health-related quality of life in patients with bipolar disorder. *Arch Women's Ment Health.* 2013;16(4):317–23.
- Mengi, A. & Aygur, R. S. (2018). A Study of Individuals with Bipolar Disorder: Case Study . *Black Sea Journal of Social Sciences*, 10 (19), 553-571. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/ksbd/issue/41531/501287>

- Michalak EE, Yatham LN, Lam RW (2005) Quality of life in bipolar disorder: a review of the literature. *Health Qual Life Outcomes* 3:72.
- Miklowitz DJ, Otto MW, Frank E, Reilly-Harrington NA, Kogan JN, Sachs GS, Thase ME, Calabrese JR, Marangell LB, Ostacher MJ, Patel J, Thomas MR, Araga M, Gonzalez JM, Wisniewski SR (2007) Intensive psychosocial intervention enhances functioning in patients with bipolar depression: results from a 9-month randomized controlled trial. *Am J Psychiatry* 164:1340–7.
- Miskowiak K, Burdick K, Martinez-Aran A, Bonnin C, Bowie C, Carvalho A, Gallagher P, Lafer B, López-Jaramillo C, Sumiyoshi T, McIntyre R, Schaffer A, Porter R, Torres I, Yatham L, Young A, Kessing L, Vieta E (2017) Methodological recommendations for cognition trials in bipolar disorder by the International Society for Bipolar Disorders Targeting Cognition Task Force. *Bipolar Disord* 19:614–626.
- Miskowiak KW, Ehrenreich H, Christensen EM, Kessing LV, Vinberg M (2014) Recombinant human erythropoietin to target cognitive dysfunction in bipolar disorder: a double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled phase 2 trial. *J Clin Psychiatry* 75:1347–1355.
- Miskowiak KW, Vinberg M, Macoveanu J, Ehrenreich H, Køster N, Inkster B, Paulson OB, Kessing LV, Skimminge A, Siebner HR (2015) Effects of erythropoietin on hippocampal volume and memory in mood disorders. (“2022 - psykiatri-regionh.dk”) *Biol Psychiatry* 78:270–277.